

FATIGUE AND IMPACT STRENGTH OF ARAMID/GLASS HYBRID LAMINATES FOR MARINE USE

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ABSTRACT

Fatigue and impact strength of aramid, glass and their hybrid composite laminates are examined and the hygrothermal effect on the fatigue fracture is discussed in order to determine the design criteria for naval applications. Seven kinds of glass, aramid and aramid/glass hybrid laminates are fabricated by hand-layup technique and used for the tests. Flexural fatigue tests are carried out in air and in hot water, and the fatigue life is estimated with a special consideration on the stiffness reduction. Fatigue strength of each material system is summarized by the S-N diagram and is classified according to the fracture mode. It is also shown that the fatigue strength is remarkably reduced under the hygrothermal condition. Base line data for fatigue strength design are obtained experimentally. Flexural impact strength and fracture energy are measured under three-point flexural and multiaxial loading by using an instrumented drop-weight impact testing machine. The results are compared with the static test results and the effects of loading rate and stacking sequence on the impact strength are discussed.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Fatigue; Impact; Hybrid; Fiber/Aramid; Fiber/Glass; Fabric; Strength; Test/Evaluation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Aramid/glass hybrid composites have potentially excellent mechanical properties under dynamic loading and are feasible for application in marine structures /1/. The hybrid effects of aramid/glass hybrid composites, especially the effect on dynamic properties /2/, have not been well clarified especially on dynamic properties. The fracture and damage accumulation processes under cyclic and impact loading have become a matter of major interest. In the present paper the fatigue and impact properties of aramid, glass and aramid/glass hybrid

laminates are investigated and the effects of reinforcement and stacking sequences on the dynamic properties are discussed.

2. MATERIALS

Aramid, glass and commingled aramid/glass roving fabric reinforced unsaturated polyester resins were used in the tests /3,4/. Stacking sequences of the test materials and their nominal thickness are listed in Table 1. Laminates C, I and G are roving-cloth reinforced composites, laminate J is a glass-mat reinforced composite, and laminates E1G, E1K and H1 are mat/roving-cloth reinforced composites. The aramid, glass and aramid/glass hybrid laminates were fabricated by using hand-layup technique, similar to the process for fishing boat construction. The cross sectional view of the aramid/glass commingled roving fabric is shown in Fig. 1.

Rectangular specimens were cut from the laminates. Width of the 3-point flexural fatigue test specimen is 25 mm and the span lengths between supporting noses are 56 mm for specimens C, I and G and 90 mm for specimens E1G, E1K and H1, respectively. Some specimens are conditioned in 80°C hot water for 40 days before the fatigue tests and the others are in air at room temperature. The widths and span lengths of the 3-point flexural impact test specimen are 10 mm and 60 mm, respectively. The size of square specimen for multiaxial impact test is 152 mm x 152 mm and the rim with a diameter of 127 mm was fixed to the supporting fixture to apply multiaxial impact stress as shown in Fig. 2.

TABLE 1 Specifications of laminates tested

Specimen	Laminae stacking	Thickness (mm)	Vf (%)		
C	A x 4 plies	3.59	37		
I	R x 5 plies	3.12	36	A : Kevlar 49 roving fabric	458 gr/m ²
J	M x 3 plies	3.24	17	R : Glass roving fabric	580 gr/m ²
G	(A/R) x 5 plies	3.62	41	M: Glass chopped mat	450 gr/m ²
E1K	M/A/MM/A/M	5.48	23		
E1G	M/R/MM/R/M	5.33	22	A/G : Kevlar49/glass roving fabric	538 gr/m ²
H1	M/(A/G)/MM/(A/G)/M	5.41	24		

Fig. 1 Sectional view of laminate G

Fig. 2 Schematic figure of multi-axial impact specimen

3. TEST METHODS

An electrohydraulic testing system was used for the 3-point flexural fatigue tests. The minimum to maximum load ratio and the loading frequency was fixed at 0.1 and 5 Hz, respectively. The initial peak load was selected 40,50,60 70 and 80% of the static flexural strength and the test was carried out under displacement control. Maximum flexural stress, σ_{\max} , is given by Eq. 1.

$$\sigma_{\max} = \frac{3P_{\max}L}{2bt^2} \quad (1)$$

where, P_{\max} is maximum load, L is span length, b and t are width and thickness of the specimen, respectively. The fatigue fracture was defined as 20% stiffness loss in the load versus deflection curve.

Instrumented drop-weight impact test system was used for 3-point flexural and multi-axial impact tests. The acceleration of the dart was measured by using a transducer and the initial velocity was also detected with a sensor detector just before the impact. The acceleration signal was amplified, A/D converted and stored in the memory of a microcomputer. The original wave form was conditioned by using digital filtering techniques /5/. The velocity, $v(t)$, and displacement, $\delta(t)$, of dart and the applied load, $P(t)$, can be obtained by integrating the detected acceleration, $\alpha(t)$. Three-point flexural impact strength is estimated by using Eq. 1.

In order to obtain the multi-axial impact strength, a stress distribution of an isotropic circular plate which is rigidly clamped at the rim is calculated, assuming an uniform distributed load at the center of the plate.

$$\sigma_{\max} = \frac{3P_{\max}(1-\nu)}{8\pi t^2} \left[\frac{r^2}{a^2} + 4 \ln\left(\frac{a}{r}\right) \right] \quad (2)$$

where, a and r are radii of the specimen and the load distributing area, respectively. ν is Poisson's ratio. r is assumed to be equal to the nose radius of the falling dart.

Absorbed energy, E, during impact fracture is defined as Eq.3 for the 3-point flexural and multi-axial impact specimens.

$$E = \int_0^{\delta} Pd\delta/B \quad (3)$$

$$B = \begin{cases} bt & \text{for 3-point flexural impact specimen} \\ \pi r^2 t & \text{for multiaxial impact specimen} \end{cases}$$

4. FATIGUE PROPERTIES

Load versus deflection curves under static flexural loading are shown in Fig. 3. Figure 4 shows fatigue behavior of specimens I, J and C laminates. Curves are fitted to the experimental data using the least squares method. Specimens C and J give similar S-N curves, though the rate of fatigue degradation of specimen C is slightly higher than specimen J. On the other hand, specimen I shows excellent fatigue resistant behavior in the three laminates. We have defined fatigue limit as the fatigue strength at 10^6 cycle.

Fig. 3 Load-deflection curves of static flexural test

Fig. 4 S-N curves of specimens C, I and J

S-N behavior of specimen G is compared with those of specimens I and C in Fig.5 , which denotes intermediate fatigue behavior. Figure 6 shows the S-N curves of specimens E1G, E1K and H1. The static strength of E1K which contains aramid cloth layer is approximately 20% higher than E1G. E1K maintains its strength advantage in the low cycle fatigue region under 10^4 cycles, though it gives lower fatigue limit at 10^6 cycles because of the steeper degradation of fatigue strength. On the other hand, specimen H1 which contains commingled aramid/glass hybrid cloth layer, indicates the highest fatigue strength after 10^4 cycles in the three kind of hybrid laminates. This behavior can be understood as the hybrid effects in the fatigue strength.

Figure 7 presents a comparison between the static and fatigue strength of all materials tested in the present paper. The results indicate that specimen C has the lowest fatigue strength, but

Fig. 5 S-N curves of specimens C, I and G

Fig. 6 S-N curves of specimens E1K, E1G and H1

Fig. 7 A comparison between the static flexural strength and fatigue limit strength of the laminates

Fig. 8 S-N curves of specimen C tested in air and in water

Fig. 9 S-N curves of specimen I tested in air and in water

Fig. 10 S-N curves of specimen E1K tested in air and in water

specimen H1 gives a reasonable fatigue strength among the mat-roving fabric reinforced laminates. Specimen I has the highest strength properties both in the static and fatigue tests.

Figure 8 and 9 show comparison between S-N curves tested in air and in water. The flexural fatigue test was carried out in water at 20°C after conditioning in 80°C hot water for 40 days. The results indicate that fatigue strength in the water absorbed condition in water is nearly 50% lower than in air. The same behavior is observed in specimen E1K as shown in Fig.10. The fatigue strength reduction due to water absorption is around 50% in all specimens. It means that the environmental test condition is very severe on the laminates.

5. IMPACT PROPERTIES

Figure 11 shows typical stress versus deflection curves obtained by the three-point flexural impact tests. Mass of the dart is 1 kg and dropping distance, H, of 900 mm and 1500 mm give initial impact velocity of 4.2 m/s and 5.4 m/s, respectively. The laminate systems vary the impact responses, for example, specimen C shows the most ductile fracture and specimen I shows the most brittle fracture. There is no appreciable difference between impact and static responses. Figure 12 lists the impact strengths of the test specimens. We found the same tendency of strength in the impact test as in the static and fatigue tests. Figure 13 shows impact energies, E_M and E_T , which are defined as the absorbed energies upto the maximum load and upto the final breakage, respectively. The results indicate again that specimen C breaks in a ductile manner and specimen I breaks in a brittle manner. On the other hand, mat/roving fabric laminates, E1K, E1G and H show intermediate fracture, which is the result of energy absorption in the glass-mat layers. Figure 14 shows the typical stress versus displacement diagram of multiaxial impact test. Mass of the dart is 4 kg and dropping distance is 1250 mm. All the data indicate ductile fracture after reaching maximum load. The ductile load versus deflection curves may be the result of the multiaxial stress conditions. The dropping distance was fixed to be 1250 mm. The absorbed energies are compared in Fig. 15. Pictures of the penetrated specimens are shown in Fig. 16.

Fig. 11 Examples of stress versus deflection curves obtained by the three point flexural impact test

Fig. 12 A comparison between impact and static strengths in the three point flexural impact test results

Fig. 13 Average impact energy, E_m and E_t , of the three point flexural impact tests

Fig. 14 Examples of stress versus deflection curves obtained by the multiaxial impact test

Fig. 15 Averaged impact absorbed energy, E_m and E_t , of the multiaxial impact tests

Fig. 16 Photos of penetrated multi-axial impact specimens

6. DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

The flexural fatigue tests under constant deflection control and the three-point flexural and multi-axial impact tests were carried out in order to investigate the dynamic performance of the hand-layup unsaturated polyester matrix laminates reinforced with four kinds of reinforcements which include aramid(kevlar 49) cloth, glass-cloth, commingled aramid / glass cloth and glass mats. The glass-mat, commingled aramid / glass fabric reinforced laminate, H1, as well as the glass fabric reinforced laminate, I, gives good performance in cyclic loading. Water absorption in hot water remarkably decreases the fatigue limit, and the strength reduction reaches 50%. It is shown that specimens I and H1 exhibit excellent dynamic properties both in fatigue and impact as well as static properties, although the aramid fabric laminate C by itself gives relatively low impact strength. Aramid/glass hybrid laminates H1, which is properly reinforced with commingled aramid/glass fabric represents excellent properties under the fatigue and multi-axial impact loading.

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